

Complexity of Structured Text Function Blocks in IEC 61499

Thank you very much for your interest in this survey!

My name is **Lisa Sonnleithner** and I am a researcher at the **CDL VaSiCS, LIT | Cyber-Physical Systems Lab** (<https://www.jku.at/en/lit-cyber-physical-systems-lab/>) lead by **Prof. Rick Rabiser** and **Prof. Alois Zoitl**. My research focuses on IEC 61499 software architecture and software metrics.

The questions in this survey aim to investigate the **complexity of IEC 61131-3 Structured Text Function Blocks in IEC 61499**.

The goal of this survey is to assess developers' perception of complexity of IEC 61131-3 Structured Text Function Blocks in IEC 61499, i.e., how hard it is to understand a Function Block. We will use this information to assess which metric best represents that perception. This metric can then be implemented in any IEC 61499 development tool to provide meaningful feedback during the development process and help improve software quality. Therefore, by participating in this survey you not only help us with our research but you will also benefit from better tool support in the future!

The **Structured Text code** used for the questions is mostly taken from **real libraries**.

Completing this survey will only take around **10-15 minutes**.

You are coming from an IEC 61131-3 background and have no idea what an IEC 61499 Simple Function Block is?

A Simple Function Block encapsulates an algorithm. The standard would allow algorithms in any programming language, however, we will only consider Structured Text algorithms.

The interface of a Simple Function Block defines its input parameters on the left and output parameters on the right. Internal variables are also possible. The algorithm can be called via its input event and will send an output event once it is done.

As an example, this Simple Function Block with the name **CONCAT** has two input parameters **IN1** and **IN2** of type **STRING**. When an event arrives at the input **REQ**, the algorithm inside the block is started. As the name suggests, it combines the two input strings to a new string that is written to the output **OUT**. Once this is completed, an event on the output side is generated to indicate the algorithms completion.

We also aim to publish the results of this survey, of course in an **abstracted, anonymized** way.

If you have any questions about the survey please email us: lisa.sonnleithner@jku.at

There are 19 questions in this survey.

General Questions

Where are you currently located?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Prefer not to say
- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- American Samoa
- Andorra
- Angola
- Anguilla
- Antarctica
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas, The
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bermuda
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Bouvet Island
- Brazil

- British Indian Ocean Territory
- British Virgin Islands
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina Faso
- Burma
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde
- Cayman Islands
- Central African Republic
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Christmas Island
- Cocos (Keeling) Islands
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the
- Congo, Republic of the
- Cook Islands
- Costa Rica
- Cote d'Ivoire
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Curacao
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- Ecuador

- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia
- Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas)
- Faroe Islands
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- France, Metropolitan
- French Guiana
- French Polynesia
- French Southern and Antarctic Lands
- Gabon
- Gambia, The
- Gaza Strip
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Gibraltar
- Greece
- Greenland
- Grenada
- Guadeloupe
- Guam
- Guatemala
- Guernsey
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Heard Island and McDonald Islands
- Holy See (Vatican City)

- Honduras
- Hong Kong (SAR China)
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Isle of Man
- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jersey
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Korea, South
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macau (SAR China)
- Macedonia
- Madagascar

- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Martinique
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mayotte
- Mexico
- Micronesia, Federated States of
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Montserrat
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Caledonia
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- Niue
- Norfolk Island
- Northern Mariana Islands
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau

- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay
- Peru
- Philippines
- Pitcairn Islands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Puerto Rico
- Qatar
- Reunion
- Romania
- Russia
- Rwanda
- Saint Barthelemy
- Saint Helena, Ascension, and Tristan da Cunha
- Saint Kitts and Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Martin
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Sint Maarten
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia

- South Africa
- South Georgia and the Islands
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Svalbard
- Swaziland
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan, Province of China
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Timor-Leste
- Togo
- Tokelau
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Turks and Caicos Islands
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States
- United States Minor Outlying Islands
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu

- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Virgin Islands
- Wallis and Futuna
- West Bank
- Western Sahara
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

What is your age?

❗ Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Under 25
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- Over 55

What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?

❗ Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Apprenticeship
- High School Diploma
- Technical High School Diploma
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctorate Degree

Other

To which area of activity does your employer belong to?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Academia
- (Plant) Manufacturing
- Special Purpose Machinery
- Standardized Machinery
- Other

In which market does your employer mostly operate?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Aerospace
- Automotive
- Chemical industry
- Foods
- Medicine/Pharma
- Metallurgic industry
- Military
- Research
- Robotics
- Other

Background

How much experience in IEC 61131-3 Structured Text programming do you have?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- None
- Less than 1 year
- 1 year to 5 years
- 5 years to 10 years
- more than 10 years

How much experience in IEC 61499 programming do you have?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- None
- Less than 1 year
- 1 year to 5 years
- 5 years to 10 years
- more than 10 years

How much experience in other programming languages do you have?

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- None
- Less than 1 year
- 1 year to 5 years
- 5 years to 10 years
- more than 10 years

The goal of this Function Block is to perform a hysteresis function.

We provide two implementation variants of this functionality. Please rate how difficult each variant is to understand.

Interface

Variant 1

Internal Variables

Name	Type
-	-

Code

```

1 IF IN < LOW THEN
2   Q := FALSE;
3   MID := FALSE;
4 ELSIF IN > HIGH THEN
5   Q := TRUE;
6   MID := FALSE;
7 ELSE
8   MID := TRUE;
9 END_IF;

```

Variant 2

Internal Variables

Name	Type
-	-

Code

```

1 IF Q = TRUE THEN
2   IF IN < LOW THEN
3     Q := FALSE;
4   END_IF;
5 ELSE
6   IF IN > HIGH THEN
7     Q := TRUE;
8   END_IF;
9 END_IF;
10 MID := IN > LOW AND IN < HIGH;

```

1 - understandable at first glance

...

10 - impossible to understand

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Variant 1	<input type="radio"/>									
Variant 2	<input type="radio"/>									

Please rate how hard these boolean expressions are to understand.

1 - understandable at first glance

...

10 - impossible to understand

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
a AND b	<input type="radio"/>									
a AND b AND c AND d	<input type="radio"/>									
a AND b AND c AND d AND e AND f	<input type="radio"/>									
a AND b OR c AND d	<input type="radio"/>									
a OR b AND c OR d	<input type="radio"/>									
a OR (b AND c) OR d	<input type="radio"/>									

Open Feedback

In your experience, what makes a Simple Function Block / Structured Text algorithm hard to understand?

Please write your answer here:

Do you have any other feedback for us?

With regard to the survey, the questions, any other experiences, ...

Please write your answer here:

Thank you very much for your time and for participating in this survey!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.